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METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES TO DESIGN THE MODEL OF A SERVICE-ORIENTED STATE DURING SOCIAL TRANSFORMATIONS

The paper improves the methodological basis of service-oriented state development in the context of public administrating of public service provisions by defining the following systemic principles: strategic sequence; duality; institutional architecture; structural properties.

The paper show that the real sign of a formed service-oriented system during social transformations is existence of systemic, cognitive-informational and integrated characteristics, which determine development of an actor-oriented mechanism of service provided by public authorities when resources are limited, with taking into account the criteria for determining their content, structure and dynamics, as well as the priorities of state reforms.

An original concept of functioning and development of the public administrative system for service delivery is formulated in the context of public service provision. The concept is based on the principles of the systemic and synergetic approaches, differentiated by institutional and theoretical basis and service provision become a checkpoint for evaluation of public authority effectiveness.

The paper proves that the input dominant factor is subjectivity. This factor forms the basis of the actor-oriented approach, which, in turn, is aimed at implementation of service-oriented concept of public administration functioning and development during reorganisation of the overall administrative system. The paper proves that the actor orientation means a set of methodological principles of subjectivity, including: subjectivity as an essential characteristic of an actor, subjectivity of the environment, institutionalization of subjectivity, modelling of subjectivity.

Keywords: *service-oriented state, servicization, dominant ideas, criteria, subjectivity, public administration, service-oriented system, concept, many-actors system, environment, public services.*

Problem setting. Essential interpretations of the “service-oriented state” notion is delusive because the methodological principles of such state development in the conditions of social transformations have not been substantiated sufficiently yet. Given that the state is a structural element of the political system and it functions on the basis of interactions between its actors, such as authorities, civil society institutions, business structures, etc., it is worthwhile to study in details these in-

teractions as a system and to use for this purpose the actor-orientation approach to determine the methodological dominant ideas of the concept of a service-oriented state development.

Analysis of recent researches and publications. Appropriate aspects of this issue are examined in the scientific works of such researchers as G. Atamanchuk, who studies formation of the public administration system on the base of interactions and features of corresponding administrative (object-object, actor-actor and object -actor) relations in time and space; V. Bakumenko, who defines the management process as a set of continuous interrelated actions and functions of actors aimed at certain goal achieving in the context of relations between an actor and an object of managerial decisions; I. Derevianko, who defines actors of service provision and factors of their interactions with other actors; Yu. Zaitsev, who examines principles of the systemic paradigm and analyzes structure of a social state in the subjective context; G. Kleiner, who develops the systemic paradigm for economic management; T. Serbinska, who develops a causal model for modelling of a public administrative actor, the model help to determine the hierarchical nature of the public administrative “actor” and to understand its content and knowledge; P. Petrovsky, who emphasizes that the humanitarian paradigm, uniting modern human knowledge and humanitarian means, is the theoretical and methodological basis for understanding of social actors; S. Chistyakov, who investigates actors of economic interactions in a society developing as a network. Paying tribute to their scientific work, we should note that corresponding studies do not lose their relevance in the present.

Paper objective. The paper objective is to substantiate our methodological approach to the modern actor-oriented system of public administration at public service provision. This approach adds to the existing established structure the following dominant ideas: flexibility, participation, subsidiarity, hierarchy, adaptability, functionality, complemented by actor-oriented (reflexivity, servicization, consistent liberalization, co-evolution, holism, precision in monitoring and control) and systemic (strategic sequence, duality, institutional architecture, structure) principles, important during social transformations.

Paper main body. Let us note that service-oriented state as a socio-political organization has the following features: deterministic social effectiveness, encouraging formation of such public power relations in society that are voluntarily recognized by this society, and these power relations are complex, open and a subject to public control; decentralized diversification of power exercising, moreover, functioning of state and public institutions should contribute to harmonization of social values both at the state level and at the level of civil society; the legal social and just nature of the state and its sovereignty, ensuring the unity of the state and its law as forms of human existence, and with which individuals obtain opportunities to develop their own abilities and realize their own essence; a service model of public administration, introducing of service institutions that changes interactions of public authorities with the population [5, p. 23].

Formation of a service-oriented state in Ukraine in the conditions of social transformations is undeniably topical but quite problematic. Solution to this extremely important problem helps implement the institutionalization model of the modern public administrative system with service provisions and influences outcomes of modern transformations. That is why, we are going to study the service-oriented system of public administration and identify the parameters of its development by using the systemic analysis and its principal approaches to development of methods and techniques, as well as to formation and implementation of the functioning mechanisms of service-oriented state, first of all, as a service-oriented system in the context of reforms in Ukraine.

It should be noted that relations and links between elements of interpersonal communications, in general, determine the specific features of the actor-oriented approach [6, p. 119-123]. Namely, development of such a complex service-oriented system from the set of elements, which create the actor-oriented public administration system in the context of regulated provided public services, leads to a qualitative transition. This transition is stipulated by the corresponding quantitative changes as for purposefulness, breadth and depth of relations between the service-oriented mechanism and the state service functions, as well as its separate mechanisms. Therefore, the real sign of the formed service-oriented system during social transformations is systemic, cognitive-informational and integrated characteristics that are present in its defining elements and provide service technologies. This gives opportunities for formation of an actor-oriented mechanism for services provided by public authorities when resources are limited, taking into account the priorities of the Ukrainian state reforming.

Due to the existing dominant approaches within the state administration theory: structural, behavioural and functional, the actor orientation is revealed through the attributes of an actor's sufficiency: goal-setting, goal-achievement, selection of social-economic behavioural models, means and levers of influence, self-control, conscious activities [11, p. 19-20].

In this context, it is expedient to consider the scientific concept of T. Serbinskaya concerning the essence and trends of modelling of the state administrative actors. This national researcher proposes multilevel understanding of state administrative actors (which, in our case, can be applied to public administrative actors), which include three levels: a civil servant or a citizen, a state body or a citizen group, a nation (society as a whole). For a holistic systemic reflection of the "state administrative actor" notion, the scientist proposes a model based on a psychological systemic approach and its causative component [12].

The factor of subjectivity creates the systemic basis of the actor-oriented approach to implementation of the service-oriented concept of public administration functioning and development in the context of overall administrative system reengineering. In this case, the actor-orientation means *a set of methodological principles of subjectivity*, including: subjectivity as an actor's essential characteristics, subjectivity of environment, institutionalization of actors, modelling of subjectivity (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Methodological dominant ideas of the modern actor system of public administration for public service provision.

Due to this, subjectivity as an actor's essential characteristics acts as a qualitative attribute directly attributable to all actors of political, social-economic, legal, party systems. Subjectivity is a manifestation of their essential features and has a certain potential for development. This principle is detailed in such actor's qualities: activity, responsibility, trust.

We should recognize that subjectivity of the environment is implemented within a certain space – political, social-economic, and legal – due to the mechanism for specific subjectivity implementation in a many-actors system. According to this principle, the many-actors environment is defined as the space of actors-elements united by the joint work, communications and behaviour, where actor-actor relations are constructed [7, p. 44-45].

The institutionalization of subjectivity means institutionalization of subjective properties and attributes, that is, the transfer of an actor's functions from an individual to institutional actors (from the state to public organizations and a business structures), with subjectivity loss by the first actor and emergence of an integral actor. Institutional actors are formed through institutionalization of activity properties of actors-individuals and integral actors of the lower levels through the mechanism of responsibility.

In parallel, examining modelling of subjectivity, we should note that it consists in modelling of subjectivity as a process of an actor creation on the political, social-economic planes; this political, social-economic actor obtain a dominant value on the plane; and such planes themselves are characterised by an integrity of ordered in time and space interactions where participants' subjectivity become a necessary condition for their successful functioning and development. Within the content of this principle, the interaction is aimed at result achievement [14, p. 290].

That is such an interpersonal interaction, when participants identify their goals based on each other's goals, transforming the internal environment for their achievement, and simultaneously achieve them by exchanging the results of participant's functioning.

The indicated methodological principles of subjectivity are positioned as a system-generating factor of servitization [4, p. 12-19]. They are the basis for creation of the actor-oriented content of the state service policy and state services, and the main criteria for determining such policy and service content, structure and dynamics.

From the standpoint of the actor-oriented approach and the basic principles of subjectivity, *we propose the methodological dominant ideas for the concept of a service-oriented state* in the context of service provision by its actors and development of its environment in order to assess effectiveness of public authorities and to take into account detailing criteria of servitization. It should be noted that the first criterion of the actor-actor orientation of public administration is rejection of the actor-object orientation and acceptance of the actor - actor and the actor – many-actors ones [15, p. 51-59]. So, there must be compliance with the principles of following interactions: “actor-actor” (ensuring behavioural activities and com-

munications) and “actor-environment” (actualization of interactions between subjective positions).

Note, that dominant “actor – many-actors” orientation over “actor - actor” one is associated with understanding of an actors’ functioning along with other actors, and their interactions acts as the environment. In the situation of the actor - actor orientation, interacting participants are opposed to each other, within “actor – many-actors” orientation, actors are not only identified, but also included in a community significant for them [2; 4, p.235].

The first situation is characterized by the opposition of actors from different sectors and construction of horizontal ties between them. The second one is characterized by their inclusion into one community, establishing actor-actor relations with other many-actors, based on their willingness to accept openness of another.

If a public administrative system is being made subjective, it permits us to understand inter-actors communications as a set of oriented interactions that are being changed. Mutual relations of the parties take form of exchanges with activity results and parties evaluate each other, so mutual influence is possibilities. In this case, inter-actors’ interactions should be considered as a special phenomenon of political, social-economic development of the state, as a valuable resource, appeared through the purposeful transformation of internal flows of public service producers at their interactions with the external environment [6, p.260-272]. Thus, under dominance of the “actor-actor” orientation, an object of management can be positioned as an actor (having life activity). Accordingly, under certain circumstances, not an actor becomes an object of management, but the interactions between actors (although in any system, object-object interactions are not absolute, since an actor in the system can turn into an object and, conversely, the object may be regarded as an actor).

We should note that the second criterion – the external orientation of the public administration system – allows transferring of the dominant idea for internal orientation to the external one, which is detailed in compliance with the following principles: environmental system formation [9], spatial resource accessibility for actors, maximization of the goal achievement by interaction participants through realization external actors’ interests. External actors (civil society and business entities), acting in the immediate surroundings of the state and influencing directly on identification of the goals and methods to implement the state functions, collectively form the target environment. Together with the state, the target environment forms the environmental system, creates communicative channels between actors entered into this, so the actors are provided with necessary resources. Thus, the mission of public authorities is “communication and coordination, creating conditions” [9] for orienting interactions, characterized by coordination, transformation of the internal environment and mutual exchanges. According to studies by G. B. Kleiner as for systems of this type, “the result of their activities is manifested in other system functioning” [8, 9]. Actors’ access to spatial resources is a prerequisite for their functioning as social-economic systems in order to use these re-

sources, and the actors must be active in space resource use. At the same time, these actors act as elements in the context of the actor – many-actors orientation and, at the same time, are procedural (transfer of values [9]) and projective (creation and transformation of systems [8], their internal environment) systems.

Thus, each element of a many-actor system implements subjectivity in the following way: an actor as an element of a many-actor system defines a goal formed by certain motives. In addition, the actor's motives and goals are formed as a result of the communicative and behavioural activities of many other participating actors, and mutual perception, when motives and goals of other elements of the many-actor system is taken into account. To achieve own goals, the actor performs necessary operations, that is, the principle of being active by doing something is implemented. Here, the actor is guided by certain norms and rules of behaviour, established by society through its legislation. To achieve own goal, the actor must effectively perform a given function; and the actor receives additional motivation for goal achievement if the function and the goal are matched.

In our opinion, the third criterion should be generally accepted, which determines that many-actors system elements can become subjective at determination of the actors' typology diversity. The dominant many-actors status of the public administration system can be characterized by superiority of the many-actors approach over mono-actor one for, namely, state bodies in public administrative relations. The need to overcome the dominant mono-actor approach leads to formation of a system consisted of four interrelated interactive principles: dialogue, problem stating, personalization and individualization of interactions. In this aspect, it is expedient to focus as much as possible on actors' individual features at organization of public authority services. The development of the many-actors ideology should be based on the following components: formation of the public services sphere; introduction of state-private and public-state partnership, etc. [3, c.62-80].

Before focusing on development of public authority services, the structure of a more general mechanism of inter-sectoral interactions should be considered. This mechanism will be an outcome of political, social- economic (innovative) development of actors' parity in public administrative relations of the Ukrainian state.

The essence of service development as a process is revealed in interactions between three sectors – the state, business and civil society. Service-oriented development of public authorities depends on the degree of state dominance over civil society and business (this type of interactions is influence), as well as the degree of cooperation between them (this type of interactions is cooperation).

Our civil society is mainly characterized by its weak development and lack of additional contributions to welfare [11, p. 16-18]. Businesses are mainly characterized by weak autonomy as for development of civil society organizations [13, p. 70]. Interacting constructively with the state, civil society and businesses are able to influence positively on the country development, welfare of its citizens [2].

The necessary imperative for transformations of interactions between the state, businesses and civil society is to incorporate most completely business enti-

ties' and civil society organizations' powers into socio-economic strategies of the state on the basis of becoming actors in order to ensure a stable positive dynamic of social-economic development.

As for the fourth criterion, we should note that it involves real development of service proposals of state authorities, its entities and all service providers, and not simple functioning of public administration and local self-government bodies. This criterion is elaborated within the principle of continuous development of services provided by state authorities and its entities; this general principle includes such specific (private) principles as: participations, proactive adaptation, co-evolution, and holism:

1) *participations* mean active inclusion of interacting actors into developmental processes, actors' understanding on their participation in own development and development of other interacting actors, and on their inner goals;

2) *proactive adaptation* means the ability to choose different interactive strategies as well as it means manifestations of the actor-oriented initiatives;

3) *co-evolution* in interacting actors' development means co-development of interacting systems, mutual adaptation to changes of the systems included in each other and transformation of activities under the influence of mutual goal definition and feedback (adaptation).

4) *holism* means unification of the principles of actors' coordination in the many-actors system and integration in an intra-actor space; it means definition and coordination of interacting actors' goals, development during interactions of a strategy for formation and development of mutual relations, for control (audit) and monitoring the relation effectiveness.

In turn, the developmental criterion positions a service actor into the social-economic, not functional status. Such social-economic actor, as an actor of service development, is characterized by the need for self-actualisation, an aspiration for not for satisfaction, but for sufficiency.

Conclusion. The actor-oriented approach to public administration functioning and development have allowed us to determine the following methodological principles widening the established standing: participations, proactive adaptation, co-evolution, and holism. We have formulated the methodological dominant ideas of the concept of a subjective system for public administration of public service provisions that take into account the parity of service providing actors and the environment for their development, namely: actor-object orientation, actor-actor orientation, actor –many-actors orientation, internal orientation, external orientation, mono-actor, many-actors, functioning of public administration actors, development of all service providing actors. The indicated dominant ideas create the methodological basis for a holistic concept of a service-oriented state during social transformations.

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